

Stability constants determination of homo and hetero bimetallic complexes of tmdta in aqueous solution[†]

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Abstract : Reaction of divalent metal ions, Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II}, Co^{II} and Cd^{II} with ligand L (L = trimethylenediaminetetraacetic acid) for binary and ternary complexes were potentiometrically investigated in aqueous solution at 30 ± 0.1 °C and $I = 0.1$ M (NaNO₃). The binary (1 : 1, 2 : 1) and ternary (1 : 1 : 1) complexes of ligand were formed in a simultaneous manner. In homo bimetallic system the formation of M₂L complexes occurred without formation of ML complexes while the formations of hetero bimetallic complexes follow the formation of binary ML complexes. The observed concentration of species formation of binary and ternary complexes obtained by SCOGS computer program and plotted using Origin 6.1. The stability constants of complexes were calculated by SCOGS computer program using potentiometric pH-metric titration values. The relative stabilities of the ternary complexes were found higher compared to corresponding binary complexes in terms of log β_{pqr} values.

Keywords : Potentiometric studies, homo bimetallic complexes, SCOGS.

Introduction

The ability of metals ions to enhancing and diversifying functions of bioaccumulation, chelation, nitrogen fixation, respiration, photosynthesis, signal transduction and optimal functioning of various other chemical in biological system highlighted the coordination chemistry of metals complexes¹⁻³. The complexes of divalent metals have immense biological interest because of their role in exchange and transport mechanism of trace metal ions in biological system⁴. These metals play an essential role in plants, animals, and human beings when they accumulate in excess amount beyond their permissible limits, they are recognized as pollutants^{5,6}. The complexes of divalent metal cations of copper, nickel, zinc, cobalt and cadmium have been extensively used in anti-bacterial, anti-fungal and anti cancer activity reported in previous literature⁷⁻⁹. The biochemical processes in living system performed due to presences of metal ions in trace quantities¹⁰. These metals ions whenever exist in biological fluid together with two or more metals or ligands. The formation of various simple as well as ternary (mixed metal/

mixed ligand) complexes is always possible which depend on the pH of the system¹¹. This makes possible to understand the mechanism and kinetics of interaction of metals with ligand, and open new prospects for development of selective and sensitive method to bind with biochemical molecules for determination and separation. Trimethylenediamine-*N,N,N',N'*-tetraacetic acid (tmdta) is a hexadentate ligand with a trimethylene group which is most promising universal complexones. The complex formation of tmdta with transition¹², actinides¹³ and lanthanides¹⁴ metals have been reported by several researchers reveal that tmdta forms weaker, six-membered N-M-N chelates rings compared to the analogous five-membered rings with EDTA¹⁵. In view of the growing interest in the complexes formation, it is thought worthwhile to study the binary (1 : 1, 2 : 1) and ternary (1 : 1 : 1) complexes of mixed metal in aqueous solution under biological relevant condition. In present study, the concentration of species formation and stability constants of simple, homo bimetallic, and hetero bimetallic complexes of tmdta (L) were determined by SCOGS (Stability Con-

[†]In honour of Professor M. C. Chattopadhyaya on the occasion of his 70th birth anniversary.

stants of Generalized Species) computer program using potentiometric pH-metric titration values.

Material and methods :

Chemicals and reagents :

The entire chemicals were of analytical grade and used as received without any further purification. The nitrates of transition metals such as $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Zn}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$, and $\text{Cd}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were purchased from Sigma Aldrich (USA). The high purity sodium nitrate (NaNO_3), (NaOH) and nitric acid (HNO_3) were purchased from Fisher Scientific (Mumbai). The ligand trimethylenediamine-*N,N,N',N'*-tetraacetic acid (tmdta) was purchased from TCL Chemicals with 99% purity. Double distilled deionized water was used for preparing solutions and throughout the work.

Solution preparation :

The stock solutions of ligand and metals were prepared as described in previous reported literature¹⁶. The aqueous solution 0.01 *M* of tmdta (L) was prepared by constant stirring in double distilled water and standardized against a standard oxalic acid solution. The 0.01 *M* aqueous solution of each metal nitrates were prepared and standardized by disodium salt of EDTA¹⁷. Carbonate-free 0.1 *M* sodium hydroxide solution (NaOH) and 0.02 *M* nitric acid (HNO_3) were prepared and standardized against a potassium hydrogen phthalate solution¹⁸. The ionic concentration of solution was maintained by the stock solution of 0.1 *M* sodium nitrate (NaNO_3) prepared in double distilled water. The solution of binary (1 : 1, 2 : 1) and ternary (1 : 1 : 1) were prepared for titration reported as previous literature¹⁹.

- (i) 5 ml NaNO_3 (1.0 *M*) + 5 ml HNO_3 (0.02 *M*) + H_2O
- (ii) 5 ml NaNO_3 (1.0 *M*) + 5 ml HNO_3 (0.02 *M*) + 5 ml L (0.01 *M*) + H_2O
- (iii) 5 ml NaNO_3 (1.0 *M*) + 5 ml HNO_3 (0.02 *M*) + 5 ml M(II) (0.01 *M*) + 5 ml L (0.01 *M*) + H_2O
- (iv) 5 ml NaNO_3 (1.0 *M*) + 5 ml HNO_3 (0.02 *M*) + 10 ml M(II) (0.01 *M*) + 5 ml L (0.01 *M*) + H_2O
- (v) 5 ml NaNO_3 (1.0 *M*) + 5 ml HNO_3 (0.02 *M*) + 5 ml Co^{II} (0.01 *M*) + 5 ml L (0.01 *M*) + 5 ml M(II) (0.01 *M*) + H_2O

where M(II) = $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}/\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}/\text{Zn}^{\text{II}}/\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}/\text{Co}^{\text{II}}/\text{Cd}^{\text{II}}$, L = tmdta.

The solution (i-iii) for binary (1 : 1), solution (i-iv) for binary homo bimetallic and solution (i-iii+v) for ternary hetero bimetallic complexes were used for solution preparation and keep overall volume 50 ml.

Titration procedure :

The acid dissociation constants of the ligand were determined potentiometrically¹⁹ by titrating the ligand (50 ml) solution (0.01 *M*) of constant ionic strength 0.1 *M*. A SONAR magnetic stirrer (Remi) was used for constant stirring of the solution mixtures throughout the experiment. The pH measurement was performed by an electric digital pH meter with a glass electrode working on 220 V/50 cycles stabilized by A.C. mains. The electrode of pH meter was calibrated with standards buffer solution purchased from Sigma Aldrich. The temperature of solutions (30 ± 0.1) °C and ionic strength $I = 0.1$ *M* was maintained through Ultra thermostat type U10 (VEB MLW Sitz, Freital, Germany) and NaNO_3 , respectively. The stability constants of the binary and ternary complexes were determined by titration data of 50 ml solution mixture of divalent metals (0.01 *M*), ligand (0.01 *M*), 0.02 *M* (HNO_3) and 1.0 *M* NaNO_3 . The nitrogenous atmosphere of each experiment was maintained to prevent atmospheric oxidation through the nitrogen. The formation of a complex between a metal ion (*M*) and ligand (L), is in fact usually a substitution reaction. If the metal ion M(II) combines with ligand (L) to form complex (ML_n), expressed by eq. (i) :

where n is number of ligands. Thus by knowing the values of [M], [L] and ML_n the value of *K* (stability constants) of ML_n can be computed. The general three component equilibrium of metal ligand, can be written as follows :

where, "L" stands for the ligand p, q, r and t are the respective stoichiometric coefficients. The stoichiometric

coefficients of p, q, r, are either zero or positive number, where as t is negative number for a protonic species, positive number for a hydroxy species and zero for a normal species. The protonation constants of ligand such as pK_1 , pK_2 , have been determined using potentiometric techniques²⁰ and refined by using SCOGS²¹ (Stability Constants of Generalized Species) a DOS based computer program version 1.2 (1985). The concentration distribution diagrams were plotted with the program Origin 6.1.

Results and discussion

Protonation constants of ligand and stability constant of binary complexes of previously reported¹⁴ in Table 1 were redetermined using prevailing experimental condition as those utilized for determination of homo bimetallic and hetero bimetallic complexes. The results obtained are in good agreement with previous studies²².

Table 1. Stability constant of binary system (1 : 1) metal-tmdta complexes at 30 ± 0.1 °C and 0.1 M ionic strength

System	p	r	t	$\log \beta_{pqrst}$
L	0	1	-1	7.96
	0	1	-2	10.39
Cu-L	1	0	1	-6.29
	1	0	2	-13.10
	1	1	0	17.46
Ni-L	1	0	1	-8.10
	1	0	2	-16.87
	1	1	0	17.79
Zn-L	1	0	1	-8.79
	1	0	2	-14.92
	1	1	0	16.37
Co-L	1	0	1	-8.90
	1	0	2	-17.87
	1	1	0	16.37
Cd-L	1	0	1	-17.60
	1	1	0	14.12

where p = Cu^{II}/Ni^{II}/Zn^{II}/Co^{II}/Cd^{II}, r = tmdta and t = OH⁺ are the stoichiometric coefficient.

Proton-ligand stability constant :

The protonation of tmdta was determined from deviation of titration curves plotted between Acid + ligand and free acid curve at pH 2.85–10.50. The deviation increased from pH 2.97 continuously up to pH 10.19 indicated that OH group starts to dissociate at about pH 2.97 and completes its dissociation at about pH 10.0. The previous re-

ported Irving and Rossotti's methods²³ was used for determination of proton-ligand formation numbers (\bar{n}_A). The values of formation constants $pK_1 = 10.39$ and $pK_2 = 7.96$ were obtained by the \bar{n}_A vs pH similar to previous reported literature¹⁴. The formation curve was found between 0.3862 and 1.99 which indicates that the ligand have two dissociable protons.

Metal-ligand stability constants :

Binary (1 : 1) complexes :

The binary system solution of L with metal M(II) such as Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II}, Co^{II} and Cd^{II} were titrated with 0.01 M NaOH under constant ionic strength $I = 0.1$ M NaNO₃. The solution of L was titrated with presence and absence of L-M(II). The titration curves of metals complexes shown in Fig. 1(a) were found lower than the free acids curves which is associated with complexes formation due to release of hydrogen ions. The titration curves of Acid, Acid+ L and Acid-L-M(II) was initiated from pH values approximately 2.45 to higher pH values approximately 10.50. The titration curves of Acid+ L and Acid-L-M(II) presented in Fig. 1(a) indicated that the values of free ligand and metals complex are shifted to right side from acid values. The values of Acid-L-M(II) complexes are followed the same trend and found shifting at initial pH are parallel to free Acid-L curves. But after initial pH the values of Acid-L-M(II) sharply fluctuate and curves shifted far successively from Acid-L curves. This fluctuation indicates complex formation with metal and ligand. After sharp fluctuation in Acid-L-M(II) complexes the pH values successively becomes constant due to formation of the hydroxo complexes. The stability constant of complexes were determined potentiometrically by Irving and Rossotti technique and further refined by SCOGS Computer program. The calculated values of overall stability constants of ligand and metal complexes value are given in Table 1. The concentration distribution diagram of the metals complexes are shown in Annexure A. The concentration of the monohydroxo species was found to be increases with increasing pH, attaining maximum of 83% at initial pH range 3.4–4.2. However, the concentration of monohydroxo species decreases when further increases in pH followed by concentration of the dihydroxo species.

The species concentration of binary complexes of Cu-L, Ni-L, Zn-L, Co-L and Cd-L were found to be 92, 89, 95, 96 and 90% at different pH range 7.3–7.9, 9.3–9.5,

Fig. 1. Potentiometric titration curves of binary (1 : 1) system (a), homo bimetallic binary (2 : 1) system (b), and hetero bimetallic ternary (1 : 1 : 1) (c) system of tmdta complexes.

7.4–7.6, 9.3–9.8 and 7.2–7.8, respectively. The formation of H_2L and HL species in aqueous solution occurs at initial about pH 3.3–4.3 and found that all the complexes have concentration in range of 20–45 have similar reported by pervious researcher²⁵.

In the Cu-L system the concentration of H_2L and HL species found to be 33% and 42% at pH 3.4–3.8 disappear at higher pH. The hydroxo species be and found to be 45% for $Cu(OH)^+$ and 23% for $Cu(OH)_2$ at pH range 3.8–4.0 and 6.7–6.9, respectively disappear with increasing pH indicate the metal complexes formation¹.

In Ni-L system the concentration of the $Ni(OH)^+$ (33%) and $Ni(OH)_2$ (58%) obtained at initial pH decrease with increase pH. The concentration of free Ni^{II} ion was found 98% at about pH 3.3 decrease due to formation of hydroxo and further complex formation. With increasing the pH concentration the solution becomes turbid due to precipitation of hydroxo species.

In Zn-L system formation of hydroxo species start above pH 3.3 and get maximum concentration 42% for $Zn(OH)^+$ and 45%, for $Zn(OH)_2$. In binary complex system of Zn-L the protonation of ligand occurs similar to Ni-L system. The hydroxo and free metal for binary Co-L and Cd-L system were occurs at initial pH and further becomes disappear with increasing the pH of solution. These complexes follow the similar trend in dissociation of ligand at acidic condition and formation of binary complexes at higher pH. The turbidity of solution occurred due to precipitation of hydroxo species when the binary complexes formation decreases found somewhat similar to previous reported literature²².

Binary (2 : 1) homo bimetallic complexes :

The species distribution curves for homo bimetallic complexes taken as a representative is given in Fig. 2(a-d). The binary complexes found to be existed maximum about 85–98% at pH 4.6–9.0 for all homo bimetallic complexes. The stability constants of homo bimetallic binary complexes are shown in Table 2.

The complex formation in Cu-L-Cu system start above pH 3.5 shown in Fig. 2(a) where Cu^{II} exist as $Cu(aq)^{2+}$, $Cu(OH)^+$ and $Cu(OH)_2$. The predominant complex species Cu-L-Cu exist in about 97% at pH 6.7–7.0 whereas the hydroxo species obtained 63% at pH 5.6–5.8 and 54% at pH 3.7–3.9 for $Cu(OH)^+$ and $Cu(OH)_2$. Titration can-

Fig. 2. Species formation curves of homo bimetallic binary (2 : 1) system (a) Cu-L-Cu, (b) Ni-L-Ni, (c) Zn-L-Zn, (d) Co-L-Co system of tmdta complexes at 30 ± 0.1 °C, and 0.1 M ionic strength.

not be continued beyond pH 10.20 due to do appearance of turbidity which indicates possibility of precipitation of hydroxo species of copper complexes²³.

Complex formation in Ni-L-Ni system is shown in Fig. 2(b) start at pH < 3.3. The hydroxo species Ni(OH)^+ and Ni(OH)_2 obtained at initial pH 3.3–4.4 with concentration about 42 and 72%. The free metals were obtained at 98% at initial pH and ended at the high pH. The binary complexes Ni-L-Ni start to form very small concentration at initial pH while the pH is increases the concentration of

Ni-L-Ni increases and obtained concentration about 98% at pH 8.2–8.8. The hydroxo species Ni(OH)^+ and Ni(OH)_2 are practically not exist in this pH range. After this pH the complex Ni-L-Ni decreases and followed by formation of hydroxo species, increases gradually and the solution becomes turbid, possibly due to precipitation of either or both Ni(OH)^+ and Ni(OH)_2 .

In the ternary complex Zn-L-Zn system the complex formation is shown in Fig. 2(c) which start from initial pH similar to Cu^{II} and Zn system. The formation of H_2L

Table 2. Stability constant of homo-metallic binary system (2 : 1) metal-tmdta complexes at 30 ± 0.1 °C and 0.1 M ionic strength

System	p	q	r	t	log β _{pqrst}
L	0	1	0	-1	7.96
	0	1	0	-2	10.39
Cu ^{II}	1	0	0	1	-6.29
	1	0	0	2	-13.10
	0	0	1	1	-6.29
	0	0	1	2	-13.10
	1	1	1	0	22.38
Ni ^{II}	1	0	0	1	-8.10
	1	0	0	2	-16.87
	0	0	1	1	-8.10
	0	0	1	2	-16.87
	1	1	1	0	19.24
Zn ^{II}	1	0	0	1	-8.79
	1	0	0	2	-14.92
	0	0	1	1	-8.79
	0	0	1	2	-14.92
	1	1	1	0	18.12
Co ^{II}	1	0	0	1	-8.90
	1	0	0	2	-17.87
	0	0	1	1	-8.90
	0	0	1	2	-17.87
	1	1	1	0	21.86
Cd ^{II}	1	0	0	0	-11.60
	0	0	1	0	-11.60
	1	1	1	1	17.54

where p = Cu^{II}/Ni^{II}/Zn^{II}/Co^{II}/Cd^{II}, q = tmdta, r = Cu^{II}/Ni^{II}/ Zn^{II}/ Co^{II}/Cd^{II} and t = OH⁺ are the stoichiometric coefficient.

and HL species hydroxo species was found to be decreases with increasing pH indicating the metal ligand complex formation. The hydroxo species at this pH partially formed due to metal react with water molecules. The water molecules split into hydroxide and hydrogen ion in aqueous solution which help in increasing of pH. With increasing of pH the concentration of hydroxo species disappear and start to form binary Zn-L-Zn complexes. The maximum concentration of Zn-L-Zn complexes obtained 98% at pH 5.3–5.8 without ML complex formation indicates simultaneous complexes formation found similar with previous literature²⁷.

Concentration curve of ternary complexes Co-L-Co is shown in Fig. 2(d). With increasing pH the concentration of protonated ligand species H₂L < HL increases. The concentration of hydroxo species Co(OH)⁺ and Co(OH)₂

obtained about 84% at initial pH 3.3–3.7 and 58% at pH 8.3–8.4, respectively. With increasing pH the concentration of hydroxo species Co(OH)⁺ disappeared and getting to start the formation of M₂L. The binary complex Co-L-Co was found about 92% in the pH range 8.5–8.9. At higher pH the formation of Co(OH)₂ species increases gradually and the solution becomes turbid. The formation curve demonstrates that at the starting point M₂L complex formation is negligible. Both the hydroxo species is dominated that time but when the concentration of M₂L complex initiate to form the hydroxo species gradually decreases indicate M₂L complex formation with increase in pH indicates simultaneous complexes formation²⁸.

Ternary (1 : 1 : 1) hetero bimetallic complexes :

The formation of ternary hetero bimetallic complexes between selected metal ions and the ligand was obtained through a stepwise or simultaneous mechanism depending on the chelating potential of ligand (L). The significant departure of ternary complexes of hetero bimetallic curves from the ligand curves occurred at pH range 3.5 and further increase continuously upto 10.5 due to dissociation of OH group. These deviations of metal complexes curves indicate metal ligand interaction in ternary system. The formation curves of mixed metal complexes calculated by SCOGS indicate that complexes formation may be proceed by simultaneous mechanism confirmed by comparing between the calculated formation curves and the experimental titration data points. The formation of ternary complexes can be described by the following equilibria (charge are omitted for simplicity) :

where L = tmdta, M = Co^{II} and M' = Cu^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II}, Co^{II}, Cd^{II}.

The overall stability constants values expressed as log β_{pqrst} and given in Table 3 were calculated from SCOGS considering the acid dissociation constants of the ternary complexes as known quantities. It was reported that the

Table 3. Stability constant of hetero-metallic ternary system (1 : 1 : 1) metal-tmdta complexes at 30 ± 0 °C and 0.1 M ionic strength

System	p	q	r	t	$\log \beta_{pqrt}$
L	0	1	0	-1	7.96
	0	1	0	-2	10.39
M	1	0	0	1	-8.90
	2	0	0	2	-17.87
M-L-Cu	0	0	1	1	-6.29
	0	0	1	2	-13.10
	1	1	1	0	24.05
M-L-Ni	0	0	1	1	-8.10
	0	0	1	2	-16.87
	1	1	1	0	23.11
M-L-Zn	0	0	1	1	-8.79
	0	0	1	2	-14.92
	1	1	1	0	20.71
M-L-Cd	0	0	1	0	-11.60
	1	1	1	0	19.82

where p = M, q = tmdta, r = $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}/\text{Ni}^{\text{II}}/\text{Zn}^{\text{II}}/\text{Cd}^{\text{II}}$ and t = OH^+ are the stoichiometric coefficient, M = Co^{II} .

chelating the ligand in binary ML complexes has a tendency to undergo deprotonation from remaining groups, affording to the formation of ternary ML-M' complexes and L act as bidentate ligand, there it chelates to the metal ions through the carboxylic oxygen and amino nitrogen. In our studies the computer analysis of the pH titration data revealed that the formation of hetero bimetallic ternary complexes and corresponding protonated species were formed. The formation of binary complexes occurred at lower pH while the ternary complexes occurred at higher pH. The formation of ternary complexes 1 : 1 : 1 species only and other species show at below the pH 9 indicates the binding sites of ligand saturated at this pH.

The species distribution curves for hetero metallic complexes taken as a representative is given in Fig. 3. The ternary complexes of hetero bimetallic found to be existed maximum about 78–92% at pH 6.3–9.3 shown in Fig. 3(a-d) and their stability constants are shown in Table 3.

The Fig. 3(a) show the M-L-Cu system protonated H_2L and HL species of ligand is found to be at initial pH 3.2–3.6 which decreasing with increase in pH 8.2 indicates the metal ligand complex formation. The binary complex M-L was found to appear at initial pH 3.5 and obtained maximum concentration about 68% at pH range 4.8–5.0 where as the binary complex of Cu-L was found

to be 70% at pH range 5.2–5.6. As their concentration gradually decreases and formation of ternary species M-L-Cu occurs. The maximum concentration of ternary system M-L-Cu is found to be about 92% at pH range 7.6–8.2. The hydroxo species $\text{M}(\text{OH})^+$, $\text{M}(\text{OH})_2$, $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})^+$ are becomes disappear at higher pH whereas the concentration of $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ was appear in increasing order at similar pH corresponding to decrease in concentration of M-L-Cu complexes. The concentration of hydroxo species increases gradually that indicates the solution becomes turbid possibly due to precipitation of $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ species²².

Speciation curve of M-L-Ni shown in Fig. 3(b) clearly reveals the protonated species H_2L , HL, and ternary species M-L-Ni are formed in sufficient concentration. The concentration of H_2L and HL species of ligands are found to be decreasing with increase in pH rang 3.2–5.8. The concentration of HL found at 80% at initial pH range 3.4–3.7 but the gradually decreases when pH of solution increase indicating the interaction of ligand with metals. The formation of binary complexes M-L of 68% at pH 5.7–6.2 gradually decreases due to formation of ternary complex. The concentration of ternary complex M-L-Ni found to be about 82% at pH range 9.6–9.9 further decreasing continuously with increasing pH. The binary species Ni-L found to be increases with decrease in concentration of ternary complex. The hydroxo species $\text{M}(\text{OH})_2$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{OH})_2$ species is found to be negligible where as the $\text{M}(\text{OH})^+$ species originate 4% at pH range 5.2–5.5. The concentration of M(II) found at initial pH but gradually decrease when the pH of solution increase which reveals the coordination of metals with ligand and forming the complexes. The secondary metal Ni^{II} concentration also decrease with increasing pH, participate in ternary metals complexation¹¹.

The M-L-Zn system species formations shown in Fig. 3(c) were found somewhat similar with Cu-L-Ni system. The Fig. 3(c) depicted the species formation of M-L-Zn system. The binary M-L complexes in this system occurred about 48% at pH range 5.2–5.5. The concentration of Zn-L was found 51% at the initial pH 4.3–4.6 but it gradually decrease as the pH increase due to the ternary complexes M-L-Zn formation. The ternary complexes about 82% found at pH range 9.3–9.6 reveal that the formation of ternary system increases when deprotonation of binary complexes increases. The hydroxo species

Fig. 3. Species formation curves of hetero bimetallic ternary system (a) M-L-Cu, (b) M-L-Ni, (c) M-L-Zn, (d) Co-L-Cd system of tmdta complexes at 30 ± 0.1 °C, and 0.1 M ionic strength.

$M(OH)^+$ and $Zn(OH)^+$ are disappeared at increasing the pH which indicates the interaction of free metal with ligand to subsequently formation of ternary complex. While the hydroxo species $M(OH)_2$ is found to be increase corresponding to decrease of ternary complexes. The free metal species $M(II)$ and Zn^{II} was found 90% and 92% at initial pH 3.5. While gradual fall in their concentration also indicate the involvement of both the metal in complexes formation²⁰.

The M-L-Cd ternary system depicted in Fig. 3(d) shown the protonated species of ligand H_2L and HL are observed at initial pH range 3.2–3.8 gradually decrease with increasing represent the complex formation. At the initial

pH, the H_2L species is formed, and its maximum concentration 8% appears at pH range 3.5. When the pH of solution reaches to 4.5, this species has disappeared completely. HL is formed at the initial pH range 3.6–3.8 and disappears at $pH < 5.5$. These protonation of ligand participate in binary complex formation M-L and Cd-L approximately 65% and 81%, respectively at pH range 4.7–5.2. At the same pH the formation of ternary species start and get maximum concentration 94% at pH range 7.8–8.4 which gradually decreased with increasing binary species formation with higher pH. The free $M(II)$ found 66% and 74% at initial pH range 3.2–3.6 gradually disappeared with increasing pH reveal the metal complexation. The

formation of $M(OH)_2$, and $Cd(OH)_2$ are negligible whereas $M(OH)^+$ and $Cd(OH)^+$ occurs 6% and 78% at pH range 6.2–6.4. After pH 6.4 these hydroxo species disappeared and followed by the ternary complex formation. This closely related to the literature values⁹.

Conclusion

The present studies describes the formation equilibria of binary (1 : 1, 2 : 1), and ternary (1 : 1 : 1) complexes of Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Zn^{II} , Co^{II} and Cd^{II} involving tmdta (L) ligand. The stability constants of ligand and selected metal complexes were determined by potentiometric titration and refined by SCOGS computer program. The redetermined binary system stability constants were found somewhat similar to previous reported literatures. These binary system constants were utilized for determination of bimetallic homo and hetero complexes. The binary (1 : 1, 2 : 1) and ternary (1 : 1 : 1) complexes of ligand were formed in a simultaneous manner. In homo bimetallic system the formation of M_2L complexes occurred without formation of ML complexes while the formations of hetero bimetallic complexes follow the formation of binary ML complexes. The stability constants of homo bimetallic complexes have lower values than hetero bimetallic complexes. The maximum concentration of ternary complexes occurred in the higher pH range about 6–10 while the binary species in ternary system existed in pH range 3.5–5.8.

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